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Linking coastal cultural ecosystem services to human well-being and leisure preferences: insights from the Baltic Sea region

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ABSTRACT

Coastal areas are unique socio-ecological systems that are characterised by especially high provision of ecosystem services and sociocultural significance. This study investigates cultural ecosystem services (CES) provided by coastal areas in Latvia and Estonia, with a focus on their contribution to human well-being and factors that shape recreational preferences. By using a public participatory GIS (PPGIS) survey, data from 1381 recreational users were collected. The PPGIS data were utilized to map spatial patterns of CES use, assess the perceived suitability of various coastal ecosystem related factors for recreational activities, and link these activities to human well-being benefits. Results reveal that the diversity of coastal ecosystem shapes recreational uses, with Estonia's highly indented and diverse coastline supporting a wider array of activities compared to Latvia's predominantly sandy shores. Coastal CES provide diverse range of perceived well-being benefits, with both passive and active interactions with the coast contributing to mental and physical health, though the benefits vary across different CES. The study highlights the need to integrate participatory CES assessments into coastal planning to balance social and cultural values with other development interests, supporting holistic, evidence-based management strategies for Baltic Sea ecosystems and beyond.

KEY POLICY HIGHLIGHTS

- This study shows that spending time on the coast provides a wide range of perceived well-being benefits to people, as well fosters a deeper connection to nature; recognizing the role of coastal ecosystems in supporting human well-being should be a properly recognized and integrated into decision-making.
- Several coastal ecosystem-related factors, such as beach type, presence of certain species, and landscape appeal, strongly influence recreational preferences, underlining the importance of tailoring coastal planning to specific local contexts.
- Recognizing non-material values, such as places where people rate the enjoyment of landscape as especially vital, can help avoid conflicts between cultural values and economic development, informing decisions on infrastructure projects like offshore wind parks.

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1. Introduction

Coastal areas are unique, complex and vulnerable socio-ecological systems that are vital for human well-being. They provide a disproportionately higher number of ecosystem services (ES) than other ecosystem types (Agardy et al. 2005), and are also characterised by high sociocultural significance (Brown and Hausner 2017). Cultural ecosystem services (CES), encompassing recreation, aesthetic enjoyment, spirituality, social engagement and other non-material benefits people gain from ecosystems, are closely linked to human emotion, meaning and motivation, making them crucial for well-being, with the contribution of coastal ecosystems to well-being examined in various contexts (MEA, 2005, Gould et al. 2019; White et al. 2020; Severin et al. 2022; Fudge et al. 2023).

The ecosystem service (ES) concept provides an analytical framework for assessing the benefits nature offers to people in a way that can be effectively used to inform planning and ecosystem-based management of marine and coastal areas (Guerry et al. 2012; Veidemane et al. 2024). Still, CES remain the most difficult to integrate into management due to their context-specific nature and reliance on human perception (Gould et al. 2019; Huynh et al. 2022). Unlike provisioning and regulating services, which can be quantified through biophysical indicators and linked to specific ecosystem processes, CES are considered intangible and socially constructed, relying heavily on individual perception and local cultural context (Chan et al. 2011; Fish et al. 2016; Ahtiainen et al. 2019; Gould et al. 2019).

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Another challenge in CES assessment lies in interpreting such key terms as ‘supply’, ‘flow’ (or ‘use’), and ‘demand’ of services. In ecosystem service assessments, ‘supply’ is typically understood as the natural capacity of ecosystems to generate services, while ‘flow’ refers to quantity of ES used within a specific area and time. ‘Demand’, on the other hand, represents the societal need for a given service and is shaped by multiple factors, including culturally dependent desires, needs, and preferences for particular service features (Burkhard and Maes 2017). Given that CES values are socially constructed and rooted in individual perceptions, distinguishing between ‘supply’ and ‘demand’ can be particularly challenging in this context. Furthermore, the potential for CES supply is grounded in ecosystem characteristics, while the distribution of areas valued or directly used for the enjoyment of CES is heavily influenced by socio-cultural factors, such as coastal development, settlement structure, accessibility, and other variables (Brown and Hausner 2017).

Since CES arise from human interactions with the biophysical environment, binding together elements of both social and ecological concepts (Fish et al. 2016), to map and quantify CES, it is crucial to consider both the biophysical characteristics of ecosystems and the perceptions of beneficiaries (Tasser et al. 2020; Veidemanė et al. 2024). Fish et al. (2016) offer a framework that combines culturally informed participatory research with environmental valuation methods, providing a robust approach to addressing these complexities and emphasising the indispensable role of participatory approaches in CES studies.

This logic is also consistent with the conceptual framework for the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES), which aims to interlink key elements of socio-ecological system such as nature, ecosystem services and good quality of life for the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity and ecosystem services, human well-being and sustainable development (IPBES 2014; Díaz et al. 2015). The IPBES conceptual framework is used to guide the development of regional, thematic and the global assessment reports, and intended to provide a common platform for reflection and identification of options, values and relationships with nature, rather than a comprehensive shared cross-cultural description of the world (Brondízio et al. 2019).

The Baltic Sea Region is renowned as a European leader in coastal and marine protection and sustainable development strategies (Schernewski et al. 2018). Many studies have applied diverse methods to study CES in the region – such as the travel cost method to uncover the recreational value of the Baltic Sea

(Czajkowski et al. 2015), contingent valuation method to examine the economic benefits of achieving good environmental status in Finnish waters (Nieminen et al. 2019), geotag analysis to capture the aesthetic value of the Lithuanian coast (Depellegrin et al. 2012), tourism theory of place attractiveness-based multi-criteria evaluation to examine recreational services in Latvian coastal areas (Ruskule et al. 2018), survey method to assess the importance of different CES in Finland, Germany and Latvia (Ahtiainen et al. 2019), as well as combination of survey and biophysical data to analyse recreational CES in Lithuania (Inácio et al. 2022). Still, knowledge gaps remain in linking characteristics of coastal ecosystems to cultural practices and well-being benefits.

To the best of our knowledge, no published studies have yet explored the connections between the use of coastal CES, the perceived suitability of various coastal ecosystem-related factors for recreational activities, and the resulting human well-being benefits in this region. To address this gap, our study examines the relationship between coastal ecosystem and human well-being in Latvia and Estonia through the prism of CES by using a public participatory GIS (PPGIS) approach. We also assess perception of factors determining coastal areas’ suitability for CES-related activities to identify links between ecosystem characteristics and use of CES. While we recognize that well-being benefits can also arise from indirect interactions with ecosystems (Fish et al. 2016), this study focuses on CES derived from direct physical presence and engagement with the coast.

Our study aims to answer the following questions: (1) how is the CES use distributed along the coasts of Estonia and Latvia?; (2) which factors influence the perceived suitability of coastal areas for CES?; (3) how do recreational users perceive the well-being benefits gained from spending time on the coast, and how are these benefits linked to specific CES?

By addressing these questions, we aim to contribute to the understanding of coastal CES, their connections to human well-being, as well as factors that influence recreational preferences and the implications for coastal planning and management.

2. Methods

2.1. Study area

The study area encompasses two neighbouring Baltic Sea region countries, Estonia and Latvia, located along the northeastern coast of the Baltic Sea (Figure 1).

Although both countries border the Baltic Sea, the coastlines of Estonia and Latvia exhibit distinct and diverse natural characteristics. Estonia’s coastline,

Figure 1. Study area.

approximately 3800 km long, is highly indented, dotted with roughly 1500 islands and islets, which contribute to its complex coastal morphology and rich biodiversity (Palginõmm et al. 2007). This diverse landscape encompasses sandy shores, rocky coasts, and extensive wetlands (Tõnisson et al. 2011; Palginõmm et al. 2007; Loodusveeb 2024). In contrast, Latvia's coastline is shorter, about 500 km, and relatively straight, with no islands (Eberhards 2003). It features vast sandy beaches (240 km in total) and occasional rocky stretches (Eberhards 2003) but does not possess the archipelagic features characteristic to the Estonian coast.

Both Estonia and Latvia offer a mix of developed coastal areas rich in cultural heritage and remote, pristine beaches suitable for nature-based tourism (Kurzeme Planning Region et al. 2022; Lees et al. 2023). Significant portions of their coastlines are designated as protected areas, covering 75% of Estonia's coastline and 40% of Latvia's, supporting various EU-protected habitats (Laima 2017; Roasto and Kovtun-Kante 2020).

Coastal areas in both countries are home to a substantial portion of the population, with approximately 50% of residents living in coastal municipalities, primarily in larger urban settlements (Statistics Estonia 2021; Office of Citizenship and Migration Affairs 2024). The capital cities, Tallinn and Riga, are both located along the coast and are the largest population centres. Estonia has a total population of about 1.3 million, while Latvia's population is approximately 1.9 million (Eurostat 2024).

Both countries lie in the northern part of the temperate climate zone, experiencing four distinct seasons: summer, autumn, winter, and spring.

Estonia's climate is influenced by both maritime and continental conditions, with moderately warm summers (average July temperature: 16–17 °C) and cold winters (average February temperature: –2.5 to –7 °C), and annual precipitation ranging from 550–700 mm (World Bank 2021a). Similarly, Latvia has an average February temperature of –3.7 °C and a July average of +17.4 °C, with annual precipitation between 590–870 mm (World Bank 2021b). These climatic conditions create strong seasonality in tourism, with coastal areas being popular in summer and less visited during winter (Ahas et al. 2007; Grizane 2016).

2.2. Public participatory GIS

To examine the use of CES and the associated perceived well-being benefits along the Baltic Sea coast of Estonia and Latvia, we conducted a PPGIS survey. PPGIS is a method that combines geographic information systems (GIS) with participatory approaches, and is often used to improve inclusion of values and opinions of different societal groups into decision- and policy making processes (Sieber 2006). Over the past decade, PPGIS has been successfully used to identify and map ecosystem services (Brown and Fagerholm 2015).

In this study, our target group consisted of recreational users of the coast in Estonia and Latvia. The survey was implemented using a purposive-convenience sampling approach, both online and face-to-face. The online survey was developed in ESRI's ArcGIS Survey123 platform and distributed through various channels, including social media (Facebook,

Instagram, Twitter), local municipalities, non-governmental organizations, and state institutions. Face-to-face data collection was conducted along the coastlines, complemented by the distribution of informational leaflets with QR codes at public and stakeholder events. The survey was available in English, Latvian, Estonian, and Russian, with translations reviewed by native speakers for accuracy. Before publicly launching the survey, it was tested with a diverse group of Latvian and Estonian respondents, leading to adjustments to improve the clarity of the survey questions. Considering the absence of official data on unique coastal visitors in the study area, the minimum sample size (95% confidence level, 4% margin of error) was calculated based on each country's total population. The final survey was implemented from July to December 2021, collecting 1417 responses (808 from Latvia and 609 from Estonia). Of these, 64 responses were collected via paper surveys, while 1353 were gathered through direct online links or QR code leaflets. Respondents ranged in age from 12 to 82, with an average age of 41 years. Out of the total number of respondents, 1381 stated that they do visit the seaside in their free time. Responses from individuals who stated that they do not visit the seaside were excluded from the analyses (36 responses in total). It should be noted that despite our best efforts to engage a diverse audience, female respondents were overrepresented in the study (approx. 77% female and 23% male).

The survey was organized into four sections:

- (1) **Demographics:** Age, gender, place of residence.
- (2) **Favourite Coastal Place and CES:** Respondents mapped their favourite coastal location using an interactive map and selected all CES-related activities they engage in at that location in their respective country. After, respondents were asked to select one activity of the previously selected that they consider their favourite and answer more in-depth questions about it. In the survey, all CES were presented through a list of 16 CES-related activities to ensure clarity for respondents without prior knowledge of ES. The list of activities was developed by authors based on the Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES) V.5.1 (Haines-Young and Potschin 2012). To better reflect the characteristics of the Baltic Sea coast and adapt the classification for the survey, some CICES CES classes were merged into broader categories. See further details in [Appendix I](#).
- (3) **Place Suitability:** In this section, respondents were asked to rate 15 factors in terms of how they influence the suitability of the location for practising the previously selected favourite activity, using a scale from -2 (unsuitable) to 2

(crucial), with 0 indicating no importance. The evaluated factors included both so-called objective characteristics (e.g. beach type, presence of species) and explicitly perceptual aspects (landscape beauty). However, when assessed through methods such as social surveys, all factors are inherently subjective, as they are interpreted and evaluated through each individual's personal lens. The perceptual attribute we included among the factors, namely – the beauty of landscape – differs from other factors in that it represents a more abstract and aggregated value, rather than a discrete coastal features. Nonetheless, it remains essential to include, as individuals often find it easier to relate to the overall impression of a place than to isolating and assessing specific landscape elements.

The list of all factors included in the survey is available in [Appendix II](#).

- (4) **Well-Being Benefits:** Finally, respondents identified their motivations for engaging in the favourite CES-related activity. The well-being categories included in the survey were based on literature (MEA 2005; Rogers et al. 2012; King et al. 2014; Fagerholm et al. 2020) and adapted to reflect the Baltic Sea context. The list of well-being benefits included in the survey is available in [Appendix II](#).

The complete survey questionnaire is available in [Appendix II](#).

2.3. Spatial and statistical analyses

The data collected in the survey were processed for further analysis and visualized using the packages and functions compiled under the package *tidyverse* (Wickham et al. 2019) in R (R Core Team 2024).

A systematic approach was employed to convert the survey data into CES maps. A list of the CES-related activities provided by the respondents was compiled. The activities were grouped into ES (see more details in [Appendix I](#)). For mapping purposes, data points located at a distance greater than 10 km from the coastline were excluded to prevent biases introduced by misplaced points (however, information associated with these points on the activities practised and perceived suitability of factors were included in other analyses). The remaining data points were grouped by shoreline segments, each approximately 5 km in length. To eliminate bias arising from differences in shoreline length, a normalization process was applied, adjusting the number of data points per 10 km segment to ensure consistency in the density calculations. The results of spatial analyses were further interpreted by using topographic maps and other spatial data layers, such as those indicating the locations of nature protection

areas and cultural heritage sites, supplemented by expert knowledge of the study area.

After careful consideration, we decided to perform the statistical suitability analysis at the activity level rather than the CES level. This choice was motivated by the recognition that ES may be engaged through a diverse array of activities, each potentially necessitating distinct ecosystem characteristics. The suitability analysis was performed using survey responses, drawing on the scores provided by respondents when rating list of factors in terms of their suitability for their favourite leisure activity. In the analysis, we included only those activities identified as favourites by at least 5% of the respondents in each country.

For each country, a principal component analysis (PCA), using the *prcomp* function from the *stats* package in R, was employed to assess and represent the multidimensional distribution of favourite CES-related activities in relation to the suitability of different factors for practising them. A permutational multivariate analysis of variance (PERMANOVA) was conducted using the *adonis2* function from the *vegan* package (Oksanen et al. 2024) to assess differences in environmental suitability among favourite activities. This was followed by pairwise comparisons with Bonferroni correction using the *pairwise.adonis* function (Martinez Arbizu 2020), providing a more detailed understanding of the pairwise differences in environmental preferences between activities.

To illustrate the association between favourite leisure activities and perceived well-being benefits, alluvial plots were employed using the *ggplot2* package extension *ggalluvial* (Brunson and Read 2023). This approach allowed us to intuitively observe patterns in how different recreational activities contributed to perceived well-being in both countries.

3. Results

3.1. Survey overview and spatial distribution of coastal cultural ecosystem services

A total of 1339 coastal CES locations were identified via PPGIS survey in Estonia and Latvia after excluding points beyond 10 km from the coastline. Among these, 902 points were associated with active interactions with the environment, 237 with aesthetic experiences, 142 with passive interactions, 32 with educational activities, 16 with symbolic and religious interactions, and 10 with cultural heritage. The survey results revealed that the most popular coastal CES-related activities are similar in both countries, with over 60% of respondents selecting hiking/walking, swimming, and enjoying the landscape (Figure 2). The first two activities are associated with active interactions with nature (CICES V.5.1, 3.1.1.1), while the third relates to aesthetic experiences (CICES V.5.1 3.1.2.4) (Appendix I). Sunbathing,

Figure 2. CES-related activities practiced on the coasts of Estonia and Latvia. Each bar represents the percentage of respondents who reported engaging in a specific activity during their visits to the coast. The grey dashed line indicates the 5% threshold.

a passive recreational activity (CICES V.5.1, 3.1.1.2, Appendix I), was relevant to more than 60% of respondents in Latvia. In Estonia, while sunbathing ranked as the fourth most frequently mentioned activity, its prevalence did not exceed 50% (Figure 2). The findings also highlighted notable differences in how the coast is used for leisure in Estonia and Latvia. In Latvia, indicated activities were predominantly focused on active or passive recreation. In Estonia, while recreation remains highly valued, coastal users expressed interest in a broader range of CES, e.g. with nearly 40% of respondents highlighting opportunities to observe animals and plants (Figure 2). In Estonia, 15 activities associated with different CES surpassed the 5% threshold, compared to 12 in Latvia. Fishing and kite and windsurfing were mentioned by more than 10% of respondents in Estonia, and sailing by nearly 10%, whereas none of these activities exceeded 5% in Latvia (Figure 2).

In terms of favourite activities, five activities – hiking/walking, swimming, enjoying the landscape, fishing, and kite and windsurfing – surpassed the 5% threshold in Estonia. In Latvia, four activities – hiking/walking, swimming, enjoying the landscape, and sunbathing – were highlighted by more than 5% of respondents as favourite (Figure 3). This indicates that water-based activities like sailing, kitesurfing, and fishing are more popular in Estonia, while sunbathing and hiking are more preferred in Latvia.

The spatial distribution of survey responses revealed high concentrations of CES use near major coastal cities, towns, and popular tourist sites in both

Estonia and Latvia (Figure 4). The highest use was observed around the Gulf of Riga in Latvia and areas near Pärnu, Tallinn, and Haapsalu in Estonia, despite similar ecosystem characteristics available elsewhere in the countries.

Both active and passive recreation activities cluster around accessible urban centres, such as capital cities Tallinn and Riga, once again highlighting the important role of accessibility for CES (Figure 5(a,b)).

Aesthetic experiences are broadly distributed along the coasts of both countries and often co-occur with other recreational activities (Figure 5(c)). In Latvia, this CES is mostly concentrated along the Gulf of Riga, while in Estonia it centres on the northern coast. The results also highlighted specific key locations for aesthetic experiences, e.g. scenic sites such as Jurkalne's cliffs near Pavilosta in Latvia and Paldiski in Estonia are notable hotspots for landscape enjoyment.

Cultural heritage, educational, intellectual, spiritual, and symbolic interactions with nature show a more dispersed distribution (Figure 5(d–f)). However, it must be noted that cultural heritage (Figure 5(d)) and spiritual or symbolic interactions (Figure 5(e)) were the least frequently reported CES in the survey, which may have affected the precision of the results for these services. Spiritual and symbolic interactions in Latvia appear to be distributed across remote coastal stretches as well as near the capital, Riga. In Estonia, these CES are reported primarily near Pärnu and Tallinn, where the overall use of CES is the highest. Several of the cultural

Figure 3. Favourite CES-related activities practiced on the coasts of Estonia and Latvia. Each bar represents the percentage of respondents who reported a specific activity as their favourite. The grey dashed line indicates the 5% threshold.

Figure 4. Total use of CES on the coastal areas of Estonia and Latvia. The thickness of the line represents the standardised density of responses in an area (the thicker the line, the higher the density of responses).

heritage hotspots are linked to historically significant locations, such as old lighthouses, military heritage sites and traditional fishing villages. Educational activities (Figure 5(f)) are mostly concentrated near nature protection areas and large coastal towns. In Latvia, education-related CES are frequent along the Gulf of Riga, while in Estonia, hotspots include urban centres like Tallinn and several islands. The results also showed some locations that have special nature value, e.g. Dirhami near Haapsalu in north-western Estonia and Kolka in Latvia which are internationally significant bird migration areas and clear hotspots for educational CES.

3.2. Suitability analysis of factors influencing engagement in CES-related activities

The calculated average suitability scores enabled the differentiation between selected factors that had positive, negative, or neutral impacts on the decision to engage in CES-related activities in the coastal areas of Estonia and Latvia (Figures 6(a-e) and 7(a-d)). In both countries, regardless of the specific activity practised, beautiful landscapes consistently ranked among the top three factors with the highest suitability (Figures 6(a-e) and 7(a-d)). Most of the analysed activities are preferred to be practised in close association with sandy coasts, a factor that exhibited the top or second highest suitability for all activities (Figures 6(b-e) and 7(a-d)), with the exception of fishing in Estonia (Figure 6(a)). The presence of birds was also valued when enjoying the landscape or

hiking/walking in Latvia (Figure 7(c,d)), which was also positive but had a lower influence in Estonia (Figure 6(b,c)). Other specific factors exhibited high suitability when essential for practising a particular activity, such as the presence of fish for fishing or the prevalence of windy conditions for kitesurfing in Estonia (Figure 6(a-d)), clear waters for swimming in both countries (Figures 6(e), 7(b)) and for sunbathing in Latvia (the latter is most probably due to the tight connection between sunbathing and swimming, Figure 7(a)). Factors that impair the aesthetics of an ecosystem and prevent the access or practising of activities in coastal areas have been negatively scored. The presence of beach cast, common reed or muddy beaches were consistently ranked among the factors with lowest suitability for practising most of the analysed activities (Figures 6(a-e) and 7(a-d)). Precipitations for sunbathing in Latvia (Figure 7(a)) or the presence of stony/rocky beaches for kitesurfing in Estonia (Figure 6(d)) also received particularly low suitability scores due to their implications for practicing these specific activities.

By taking a multidimensional approach with suitability scores, we identified distinct types of leisure activities based on their ecological and environmental requirements. In the PCA performed using the information gathered in Estonia (Figure 8(a)), the first two principal components (PC1 and PC2) cumulatively explained 38.2% of the variance. The presence of birds (16.4%), coastal meadows (13.9%), fish (13.1%), and other plants and animals (16.3%) were the main contributing factors to PC1, capturing aspects related to the

Figure 5. Use of different CES on the coastal areas of Estonia and Latvia. The thickness of the line represents the standardised density of responses in an area (the thicker the line, the higher the density of responses).

local biodiversity characteristics of the areas where activities are practised. The occurrence of muddy beaches (15.3%), water transparency (12.2%), prevailing wind conditions (12.7%), the presence of beach cast (12.8%), and beautiful landscapes (10.4%) showed the highest contributions to PC2, reflecting conditions associated with the physical environment and weather-related factors (Appendix III, Table S1). Beyond the high variability of the data, hiking/walking and enjoying the landscape tended to co-occur in the PCA, suggesting overall similar ecosystem characteristics required for practising them (Figure 8(a)). These two activities were segregated along PC1 from swimming and kite- or windsurfing, primarily due to the lower overall relevance of biodiversity for the latter activities (Figure 6(b-e)). Hiking/walking, enjoying the landscape and swimming clearly segregated along PC2 from kite and surfing (Figure 8(a)), given the contrasting physical conditions needed for practising these activities. These differences are mainly related to the particular

importance of windy conditions for kitesurfing and the neutral to slightly negative influence on hiking/walking, enjoying the landscape and swimming (Figure 6(b-e)). The observed differences in the PCA were confirmed by the performed PERMANOVA and associated pairwise comparisons where, although R^2 values were generally small, significant differences were identified among all activities with the exception of hiking/walking and enjoying the landscape, indicating the more similar ecosystem characteristics preferred to practice these two activities (Appendix III, Tables S2 and S3).

In the PCA analysis of data collected in Latvia, the first two components accounted for 39.7% of the variability (Figure 8(b)). Similar to Estonia, PC1 was mainly related to biodiversity components, while PC2 was mainly related to the physical characteristics of the locations where activities were practised. Coastal meadows (10.7%) and the presence of birds (14.8%), fish (14.1%) and other plants and animals (15.66%) where the main factors

Figure 6. Suitability scores of factors to practice selected CES-related activities (A: fishing, B: hiking/walking, C: enjoying the landscape, D: kite and windsurfing, E: swimming) in Estonia. Dots represent calculated average scores and whiskers 95% confidence intervals.

contributing to PC1, while the prevalence of muddy beaches (14.8%), water transparency (15.5%) and the occurrence of beach cast (12.7%) shaped PC2 (Appendix III, Table S4). Sunbathing and swimming tended to co-occur in the PCA and segregate from hiking/walking and enjoying the

landscape along PC1 (Figure 8(b), Tables S5 and S6 in Appendix III). This separation suggests that biodiversity holds relatively low relevance for sunbathing and swimming, while it positively influences engagement in hiking/walking and enjoying of the landscape (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Suitability scores of factors to practice selected CES-related activities (A: sunbathing, B: swimming, C: enjoying the landscape, D: hiking/walking) in Latvia. Dots represent calculated average scores and whiskers 95% confidence intervals.

Figure 8. Principal component analysis (PCA) biplots for CES-related activities in Estonia (a) and Latvia (b) based on suitability scores obtained for various factors. Dots represent survey responses and vectors indicate the contribution and direction of each factor relative to the principal components. The variance explained by each principal component is displayed in parentheses along the respective axes. Shaded regions represent 95% confidence ellipses.

3.3. Well-being benefits provided by CES-related activities

Most respondents in both countries identified hiking/walking as a key leisure activity contributing to both mental and physical well-being. Almost 80% of total respondents in both countries who selected hiking/walking as their favourite CES-related coastal activity, associated it with mental health benefits and over 60% with physical health benefits. Almost 50% of Latvian and over 80% of Estonian respondents indicated that the activity fosters a sense of connection with nature (Figure 9(a,b)). A smaller proportion also highlighted benefits such as aesthetic inspiration (26% of Latvians,

21% of Estonians) and a sense of belonging (32% of Latvians, 7% of Estonians) (Figure 9(a,b)). Another valued coastal leisure activity, enjoyment of the landscape, was strongly linked to a broad spectrum of perceived well-being benefits in both countries, particularly feeling closer to nature (84% of Estonians, 59% of Latvians) and mental well-being (75% of Estonians, 71% of Latvians). Other perceived benefits, such as improved physical well-being (41% of Estonians, 33% of Latvians), sense of belonging (17% of Estonians, 47% of Latvians), and aesthetic inspiration (over 30% of respondents in both countries), were also linked to this activity. Swimming was linked with a wide

Figure 9. Alluvial plots showing the relationship between practised CES-related activities (left side of the plot) and perceived well-being benefits (right side of the plot) for Estonia (a) and Latvia (b). Flows and their widths represent the connections between activities and perceived well-being benefits, with the width indicating the proportion of respondents associated with each connection.

spectrum of well-being benefits in both countries as well, especially physical (57% of Estonians, 48% of Latvians) and mental health (71% of Estonians, 64% of Latvians), as well as feeling closer to nature (81% of Estonians, 44% of Latvians). Sunbathing that was a popular favourite coastal activity only in Latvia, was primarily associated with mental well-being benefits (67%) and, to a lesser extent, with other well-being categories by Latvian respondents. In contrast, fishing that emerged as a significant favourite CES-related coastal activity only in Estonia, linked predominantly to feeling closer to nature (97%), mental well-being (71%), physical well-being (29%) and a sense of belonging and social interactions (29%), highlighting its cultural and social importance. Kite and windsurfing, noted by over 5% of respondents in Estonia, were strongly associated with physical well-being (87%) due to their physical demands, while also contributing to mental well-being (76%) and fostering a sense of belonging and social interactions (50%), suggesting a shared social significance similar to fishing. In general, educational purposes were the least frequently reported benefits of coastal activities in both countries (Figure 9 (a,b)).

4. Discussion

The presented study demonstrates participatory approach to the mapping and assessment of CES in the coastal zones of Latvia and Estonia. The online PPGIS survey, targeting recreational users of the coastal area, enabled us to gain an overview of the spatial distribution of various CES-related activities along the coast. It also allowed us to link this information to the perceived suitability of different coastal ecosystem-related factors – both biophysical and perceptual – for each mapped activity and to the contribution of these activities to respondents' perceived well-being benefits. In this study, we adopt the definitions of ecosystem service 'flow', 'supply', and 'demand' as outlined by Burkhard and Maes (2017). In this logic our results primarily reflect the use of CES or 'flow', while rating of different factors in relation to their influence on the suitability of a site for a specific activity provide insights into the capacity of coastal ecosystems to 'supply' CES and as well as can be related to 'demand'.

Clear terminology and interpretations of CES are crucial for consistent assessment and integration into decision-making. However, several different interpretations exist in the scientific literature. For example, Inácio et al. (2022) developed quantitative models to assess and map coastal CES supply, flow, and demand in Lithuania. In their approach, CES 'supply' was mapped using geospatial data, while 'flow' and 'demand' were estimated from survey responses – 'flow' by connecting the locations for recreation

selected by respondents with their points of origin and 'demand' based on average number of activities performed by respondents during visits at the coast. However, this approach did not explicitly assess how mapped supply variables influence site selection, leaving the relationship between supply, flow, and demand unexamined.

The participatory mapping applied in our study represents a social research method, which allows us to identify objective place features, as well as subjective perceptions of the place and its importance (Brown and Hausner 2017). This dual perspective – integrating biophysical information with subjective human experiences – enables evidence-based modelling of CES supply while accounting for spatial patterns of human use. The results help address trade-offs in coastal development, guide resource allocation for public access infrastructure, and optimize recreational facility management based on suitable locations and activities.

4.1. Factors determining supply and use of coastal cultural ecosystem services

Our study found that coastal areas in Estonia and Latvia are primarily used for active and passive recreation in nature, with hiking/walking and swimming being the most popular activities. These areas are also valued for aesthetic experiences, particularly for enjoying the landscape. In contrast, CES related to education, spirituality, symbolism, and cultural heritage hold relatively lower importance. These findings are consistent with a previous study in the Baltic Sea Region, which similarly identified recreation and landscape enjoyment as the most significant CES, while educational, cultural, spiritual and symbolic values were less prominent (Ahtiainen et al. 2019). Similar patterns have been observed in PPGIS studies of other ecosystem types, where outdoor recreation consistently emerges as a highly valued CES – for example, in urban forests (Baumeister et al. 2020), as well as in fjords and mountains (Hausner et al. 2015; Cusens et al. 2022).

Despite similarities in favourite CES-related activities, the overall patterns of coastal recreational use differ between Estonia and Latvia. This firstly refers to the broader range of coastal CES-related activities performed in Estonia, and second, to the type of activities reported in each country. The variety of CES-related activities depends on the multifunctionality of coastal areas and their capacity to supply CES (Pinto et al. 2024). These differences are largely attributed to the contrasting characteristics of the coastlines. Latvia's relatively straight coastline, dominated by sandy beaches, supports activities such as sunbathing, swimming, and hiking/walking – aligning with the global preference for '3S' activities (sea,

sun, and sand) (Mestanza-Ramón et al. 2020). In contrast, Estonia's highly indented coastline, with its bays, islands, rocky and stony beaches, and wet coastal meadows, fosters a broader range of interactions, including water-based activities like sailing, wind- and kitesurfing, fishing, and observing plants and animals. Interestingly, our findings differ from those of a study in neighbouring Lithuania where coastline is characterised by similar sandy beaches as the ones in Latvia. This study showed that respondents mostly preferred experiential activities such as guided tours and spa or resort use, while hiking/walking ranked low (Pinto et al. 2024). However, the Lithuanian study assessed CES demand – identifying preferred activities irrespective of availability – while the actual offer of tours and resorts was noted to be low. In contrast, our study focused on the actual use of CES, aligning more closely with service flow. These differing findings may reflect a mismatch between CES supply, flow, and demand or highlight socio-cultural differences in coastal area usage across the Baltic Sea region.

The respondents' assessments of the factors influencing the site suitability for leisure activities provided insights into their effects on CES supply. For instance, obtained results indicate an overall preference for sandy beaches and scenic landscapes when selecting locations for practicing a wide range of coastal leisure activities in both Estonia and Latvia. In addition, the multidimensional analysis of respondents' preferences for the selected factors identified two distinct groups, each linked to different types of activities. Biodiversity-related characteristics showed higher relevance for hiking/walking and enjoyment of landscape, while being less relevant for sunbathing, swimming and kitesurfing, which are more dependent on physical and weather-related factors. These findings address the intangible nature of CES by linking their supply to measurable biophysical parameters. In line with Fish et al. (2016), our approach relied on people's perceptions, connecting them to specific places and their characteristics – such as landscapes, species, and geomorphology – enabling an exploration of human perceptions in the context of material processes and entities. However, the role of ecosystem characteristics in providing CES must be considered alongside factors like accessibility, settlement patterns, and population density, which can facilitate or constrain their use (Banella et al. 2024). The importance of accessibility and proximity to residential areas in shaping the value of coastal CES has been demonstrated in numerous studies both in Europe and beyond (Fagerholm et al. 2019; Ruskule et al. 2018; Scully-Engelmeyer et al. 2021; Cusens et al. 2022). Although this study did not directly assess accessibility due to a lack of comparable and sufficiently detailed datasets from both

countries, the results reveal high concentrations of CES use near major coastal towns, cities, and popular tourist destinations. For example, Paviosta in Latvia, with fewer than 1000 permanent residents, has become a prominent lifestyle and surfing destination, where seasonal visitors far outnumber the year-round population. Similar trends are observed in other coastal towns and villages, such as Engure in Latvia and Kalana and Käsma in Estonia. Identifying such hotspots is crucial for managing seasonal pressures and mitigating potential conflicts between different user groups.

4.2. Contribution of coastal cultural ecosystem services to human well-being

Human well-being is a multidimensional concept that encompasses various components, both objective (e.g. physical health parameters) and subjective (e.g. feelings of happiness or good social relations) (Rogers et al. 2012). These components are interrelated, and together contribute to the quality of life and fulfilment. The close connection between human well-being and the physical environment is well-documented, with evidence showing that exposure to nature enhances physical health, mental well-being, and cognitive function (Jimenez et al. 2021). Positive effects of blue spaces, such as oceans and coasts, further support this relationship (Severin et al. 2022, White et al. 2020). These findings align with the 'biophilia' hypothesis, which suggests that humans have an innate tendency to connect with nature, and interactions with nature have a positive impact on our well-being (Wilson 1984).

Our results reveal that all favourite CES-related activities identified in the survey (hiking/walking, enjoyment of the landscape and swimming in both countries, as well as fishing and kite/windsurfing in Estonia and sunbathing in Latvia) are important for the perceived mental and physical well-being of respondents, as well as for fostering a sense of connection with nature. At the same time, the analysis also shows considerable differences between the well-being benefits of active and passive interaction with the coast. Passive interactions like enjoying the landscape and sunbathing are strongly connected to aesthetic inspiration, feeling closer to nature, and mental well-being. These benefits are often linked to relaxation, contemplation, and sensory enjoyment of the coastal environment, reflecting a primarily mental and emotional connection rather than a physical one (although the activities also provide perceived benefits for physical health). Active interactions with the coast such as hiking/walking, swimming, and kite/windsurfing are more strongly linked to perceived physical and mental health benefits. These activities involve physical exertion and movement,

which can enhance physical health while also providing mental rejuvenation. From this we can conclude that a more diverse coastal character, with more opportunities for active and passive interactions, is also more conducive to various dimensions of human well-being.

However, it must be noted that the relationship between human well-being and ecosystems is inherently complex and non-linear (Fish et al. 2016). The socio-cultural context, including settlement structure, cultural heritage, traditions, etc., are highly important for understanding and interpreting the spatial distribution of coastal CES and their contribution to human-wellbeing. Therefore, conducting more detailed studies at the local scale would provide valuable insights into the intricate connections between human well-being and coastal ecosystems.

4.3. Contribution of cultural ecosystem service studies to planning in coastal areas

The concept of CES supports the integration of the ecosystem-based approach in coastal development planning (Veidemane et al. 2024) and maritime spatial planning (Banela et al. 2024). Member states of European Union have developed their maritime spatial plans and many are revising them to better address recent policy ambitions of renewable energy, climate change and other maritime sectors. The ecosystem-based approach emphasizes the importance of incorporating ES assessment values, including CES, to facilitate informed discussions about trade-offs between ES in different planning scenarios and to prioritize sustainable management options (Friedrich et al. 2020; Galparsoro et al. 2021).

One potential application of CES assessment results is in spatial prioritization for the development of recreational infrastructure, enabling efficient allocation of investment and maintenance costs. Survey results indicate that sunbathing and swimming are among the most popular activities in coastal areas, making it critical to manage pollution to ensure clean, litter-free beaches and clear waters devoid of blue-green algae or excessive reed overgrowth. Accordingly, the placement of public recreational amenities should align with the spatial distribution and flow of beach users. Waste management – encompassing the density of waste bins and the frequency of clean-ups – is a responsibility of local governments. These authorities must remain informed about use trends to effectively plan and manage coastal areas, thereby maintaining environmental quality. Furthermore, given that the Baltic Sea continues to experience eutrophication (Andersen et al. 2017), measures to prevent and reduce nutrient pollution must remain a priority to meet bathing water quality standards and ensure the

sustained provision of CES dependent on environmental quality. In addition to reducing nutrient inputs from land, which alone have failed to fully mitigate eutrophication symptoms in the Baltic Sea, internal measures are needed to reduce legacy nutrients that continue to sustain eutrophication. Low-trophic aquaculture, such as mussel and seaweed sea-based farming, represents a promising nature-based solution worth exploring. Recent findings for the region highlight its potential not only to mitigate nutrient pollution but also to contribute to the supply of additional ES (Kotta et al. 2020, 2022; Vaher et al. 2024).

Our findings offer valuable insights into the interplay between biodiversity and popular coastal activities, particularly hiking/walking and landscape enjoyment. The results highlight that biodiversity-related factors play a significant role in supporting these activities, emphasizing the need for targeted conservation measures. Features such as well-maintained trails, informational signage, and guidance on responsible behaviour in nature can help safeguard natural features, especially as user numbers grow due to increased mobility and interest in exploratory activities. Additionally, designating zones for active uses (e.g. sports or events) away from sensitive ecosystems through appropriate zoning and infrastructure can provide a balanced approach, allowing for sustainable human-nature interactions while minimizing environmental impacts. The protection of biodiversity and aesthetic values of landscape has been highlighted in numerous recent studies on CES (e.g. Tribot et al. 2018; Kalinauskas et al. 2021). This issue is particularly pertinent given the rise of wind park developments in coastal and offshore areas, which alter landscape aesthetics (positively or negatively) and, consequently, the flow of CES (Hooper et al. 2017; Voltaire and Koutchade 2020; Watson et al. 2024). We concur with researchers who argue that highly valued and aesthetically significant landscapes should be incorporated into trade-off analyses during maritime spatial planning and integrated coastal zone management.

Certain activities, such as fishing and boating, necessitate specific port infrastructure. For instance, Estonia has developed over 240 ports and harbours (Estonian State Port Register 2024), while Latvia has only ten (Rijkure and Sare 2013), reflecting the greater popularity of these activities in Estonia. Although our study did not directly examine the demand for CES, research by Pinto et al. (2024) indicates growing public interest in exploring new activities within the region. Investing in harbours and port recreational infrastructure in Latvia can facilitate higher flows of specific CES.

While our study provides new data and analysis on cultural ecosystem services (CES) that can support

ongoing coastal and maritime spatial planning efforts in Europe and globally, we also acknowledge the persistent barriers to integrating such data into planning and policy-making processes. These barriers are often rooted in existing institutional rules, practices, and socio-political systems where powerful interests play a significant role (Brown et al. 2020). The varying capacities and expertise of planners, along with the challenges of effective knowledge transfer and collaboration between researchers and policymakers, are key factors to consider (Longato et al. 2021). Furthermore, cooperation mechanisms in this context tend to be dynamic and often short-lived, with relatively few evolving into long-term, stable frameworks capable of supporting the sustained integration of scientific knowledge into planning processes.

4.4. Limitations of the study and further research needs

Our study showcases an approach to linking space (i.e. places and coastal ecosystem related factors underpinning the coastal CES supply), to practices and benefits, as outlined in the conceptual framework of CES by Fish et al. (2016). While this approach provides valuable insights, further exploration of users' motivations through qualitative social research methods, such as interviews or focus group discussions, would enrich the findings. The study's results can be further contextualized by integrating the PPGIS data on CES use with biophysical datasets, as demonstrated by Inácio et al. (2022), and with spatial data on public infrastructure, such as roads, parking areas, and accommodations. As noted before, accessibility is a crucial factor in interpreting the distribution patterns of CES use; however, it was not examined in this study due to the unavailability of sufficiently detailed and comparable spatial datasets across the two countries. In addition, for future research, the perceived suitability of different factors for leisure activities offers valuable input for modelling CES supply. Incorporating these findings into biophysical models of coastal ecosystems could allow weighting of parameters and improve the accuracy of predictive assessments.

5. Conclusions

This study demonstrates the value of participatory approaches, more specifically PPGIS, in capturing both the spatial and cultural dimensions of human-nature interactions along the Baltic Sea coasts of Latvia and Estonia. By analysing the spatial distribution of CES use, the suitability of various factors for CES-related activities, and the perceived well-being benefits, this study highlights how coastal ecosystem

contributes to human well-being through both active and passive interactions.

The survey also reveals that while Estonia and Latvia share similar preferences for coastal leisure activities, there are also notable differences within the use of the coast that might be mostly linked to the natural characteristics of the coastline. The results suggest that Latvia's straight, sandy coastlines foster a more uniform set of recreational uses, whereas Estonia's diverse coastal morphology supports a wider variety of activities, including water-based and biodiversity-related engagements. The results highlight the role of coastal characteristics, such as beach type, species presence, and landscape attractiveness, in influencing recreational preferences and well-being. They emphasize the need for context-specific approaches to managing and planning coastal areas and activities.

Identified CES provide a broad range of well-being benefits. Overall, respondents associate their time on the coast with enhanced mental and physical well-being and an increased connection to nature. Passive activities, like landscape appreciation, show a stronger association with aesthetic inspiration and a sense of closeness to nature, while active interactions, such as hiking/walking and swimming, contribute more to physical health benefits. Notably, mental well-being improvements emerge as a key perceived benefit linked to both passive and active coastal interactions, ranking the highest across both categories. The survey results also support the biophilia hypothesis, highlighting interactions with nature as an essential component of human well-being.

The insights of the study are essential both for a deeper understanding of human interactions with the coast, as well as spatial planning and management, as spatial information on CES use can inform better decision-making processes for coastal development that balances cultural values with other development interests. Recognizing the significance of non-material values associated with coastal areas can help mitigate potential conflicts between cultural values and economic development. For example, areas highly valued for landscape enjoyment may not be suitable for the development of visually intrusive structures, such as offshore wind farms, due to their potential impact on the aesthetic value of the seascape. This approach contributes to the broader goal of sustainable coastal management by aligning ecological and cultural priorities with human well-being.

Future research should build upon these insights by exploring individual motivations and socio-cultural contexts through qualitative methods and linking CES use with accessibility and public infrastructure data that serve a key role in CES. This expanded understanding will further support the development of holistic, evidence-based strategies for managing coastal ecosystems in the Baltic Sea region and beyond.

Authors' contributions

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